

agar at 25 °C for 4 d to use as inocula. Plants of rice cultivar IR36 were inoculated at both seedling and early maturity stages. Lesion appearance and size were observed to determine their virulence.

Three pathogenic sclerotia-producing fungus pathogens — *Rhizoctonia solani*, *R. oryzae-sativae*, and *R. oryzae* were identified. The frequencies of the inoculum extracted from the soil were 57.3% for *R. solani*, 42.3% for *R. oryzae-sativae*, and 0.4% for *R. oryzae* (see table).

Tests for pathogenicity indicated that *R. solani* and *R. oryzae* were more aggressive on rice than *R. oryzae-sativae*. They infected rice plants at both seedling and adult stages; *R. oryzae-sativae* infected plants only at the adult stage. Symptoms caused by *R. solani* and *R. oryzae* were similar, but *R. oryzae* caused dark reddish brown or brown margins. The lesions caused by *R. solani* and *R. oryzae* were also much

Distribution of sclerotial populations responsible for sheath diseases of rice in the tropics. IRRI, 1985.

Site and population	<i>R. solani</i>		<i>R. oryzae-sativae</i>		<i>R. oryzae</i>	
	no.	Frequency (%)	no.	Frequency (%)	no.	Frequency (%)
C14						
Population A	111	53.6	96	46.4	—	—
Population B	110	52.1	101	47.9	—	—
Combined	221	52.9	197	47.1	—	—
B40						
Block A						
Apr	67	53.6	57	45.6		10.8
May	57	64.8	30	34.1	1	1.1
Block B						
Apr	74	65.5	38	33.6	1	0.9
May	64	64.7	35	35.3	—	—
Total or av	483	57.3	357	42.3	3	0.4

larger than those by *R. oryzae-sativae*, which were aggregated small spots.

We concluded that *R. solani* is the major causal organism of sheath diseases of rice in the tropics. Although less aggressive on rice than the two other fungi, *R. oryzae-sativae* was a

relatively large part of the entire sclerotial population found and may play an important role in causing rice sheath diseases in tropical areas. *R. oryzae* is very virulent on rice, but its sclerotial population was relatively low. □

Effect of plant age at inoculation on rice tungro virus development

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Twenty 10- to 20-d-old plants of variety TN1 were inoculated using 5 green leafhoppers *Nephotettix virescens* per plant after 24-h acquisition feeding.

Susceptibility was high in 10-d-old plants, with percentage of infection decreasing with increased plant age (see

Relationship between plant age, infection (%), and incubation period.

figure). The negative correlation between plant age and infection percentage was highly significant. Mean incubation

period progressively increased with plant age. These two factors were positively correlated. □

Plant parasitic nematodes associated with deepwater rice in Orissa, India

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Rice, the principal crop of Orissa, is grown in habitats ranging from fully rainfed unbanded uplands to deepwater situations with more than 50 cm water for the major part of the year.

Deepwater situations exist not only in the coastal belt at mean sea level (MSL) but also at altitudes as high as 1,067 m above MSL in the interior districts. The varieties grown under such situations are all local and take more than 180 d to mature.

In a survey of plant parasitic nematodes associated with deepwater

Plant parasitic nematodes associated with deepwater rice in Orissa India.

Nematode species	Frequency (%)	Density
<i>Aphelenchoides besseyi</i>	25	L
<i>Helicotylenchus dihystra</i>	20	L
<i>H. crenacauda</i>	25	L-M
<i>Hemicriconemoides cocophilus</i>	5	L
<i>Hirschmanniella mucronata</i>	65	M-H
<i>H. oryzae</i>	5	M
<i>Hoplolaimus indicus</i>	15	L
<i>Meloidogyne</i> sp.	5	H
<i>Pratylenchus zeae</i> ^b	10	L

^a L < 100 nematodes/250 ml soil, M = 100-250 nematodes/250 ml soil, H > 250 nematodes/250 ml soil. ^bNew record.

rice in Cuttack, Balasore (coastal belt), and Koraput (high altitude) districts, nine species were found (see table).

Hemicriconemoides cocophilus and *Pratylenchus zeae* were prevalent in the